

Quality checks for Data managers manual

The quality checks available through python scripts pay attention to attributes at different levels (biobank, collection, etc) taking care of different aspects (access policies, geolocation, etc) and raising the below warnings (in *italics*) when the data provided are not compliant with the data model.

Warnings raised about the information provided with regard to Access policies:

- *Biobank is available neither for commercial nor for non-for-profit collaboration.*
- *No sample access mode enabled and no sample access policy (description nor URI) provided for collection.*
- *No data access mode enabled and no data access policy (description nor URI) provided for collection.*
- *No imaging access mode enabled and no imaging access policy (description nor URI) provided for a collection which contains imaging data.*
- *No Data Use Ontology (DUO) term provided in data_use attribute.*
- *None of generic research use purposes provided ('DUO:0000007', 'DUO:0000006', 'DUO:0000042') in data_use attribute - suspect situation for a biobank registered in BBMRI-ERIC Directory, which is for research purposes. DUO documentation available at http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/DUO_0000007; <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/DUO:0000006>; <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/DUO:0000042>*
- *Data return is not required (missing DUO:0000029) in data_use attribute - it is recommended for biobanks to support it based on BBMRI-ERIC Access policy (but not required). DUO documentation available at http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/DUO_0000029*
- *Joint projects for sample/data/image access specified and DUO:0000020 is not specified in data_use attribute. DUO documentation available at http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/DUO_0000020*
- *At least one of non-for-profit collaboration specified on collection level but DUO:0000018 is not specified in data_use attribute (may be however intentional). DUO documentation available at http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/DUO_0000018*
- *At least one of non-for-profit collaboration specified on biobank level and not overridden on collection but DUO:0000018 is not specified in data_use attribute (may be however intentional). DUO documentation available at http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/DUO_0000018*
- *At least one of collaboration commercial specified on collection level but conflicting DUO:0000018 is specified in data_use attribute. DUO documentation available at http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/DUO_0000018*
- *At least one of collaboration commercial specified on biobank level and not overridden on collection but conflicting DUO:0000018 is specified in data_use attribute. DUO documentation available at http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/DUO_0000018*
- *Collection is disease specific but DUO:0000007 is not specified in data_use attribute (may be false-positive). DUO documentation available at http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/DUO_0000007*
- *Collection contains biological material types (xxx) but ethics approval needed DUO:0000021 is not specified in data_use attribute (may be false-positive). DUO documentation available at http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/DUO_0000021*

Key information about the people working in the biobank is checked, raising the following warnings:

- *Missing juridical person ('juridical_person' attribute is empty).*
- *Missing head person name ('head_firstname' and/or 'head_lastname' attributes are empty).*
- *Missing head person role ('head_role' attribute is empty).*
- *Missing valid contact for the biobank).*

Geographic coordinates provided are checked:

- *Invalid biobank latitude (should be a decimal number with period without any spaces or stray characters around - the surrounding quotes are added in this report): offending value xxx.*
- *Invalid biobank longitude (should be a decimal number with period without any spaces or stray characters around - the surrounding quotes are added in this report): offending value xxx.*

- *Geolocation of the biobank is likely outside of its country xxx; biobank seems to be in xxx based on geographical coordinates xxx.*
- *Reverse geocoding of the biobank location failed. (Meaning that it is not possible to find the country using the provided coordinates).*
- *Missing geographical coordinates ('latitude and/or 'longitude' attributes are empty).*
- *Invalid collection latitude (should be a decimal number with period without any spaces or stray characters around - the surrounding quotes are added in this report): offending value xxx.*
- *Invalid collection longitude (should be a decimal number with period without any spaces or stray characters around - the surrounding quotes are added in this report): offending value xxx.*
- *Geolocation of the collection is likely outside of its country xxx; collection seems to be in xxx based on geographical coordinates xxx.*
- *Reverse geocoding of the collection location failed (Meaning that it is not possible to find the country using the provided coordinates).*

Each biobank must have at least one collection registered, if not, the following warning will appear:

- *Missing at least one collection for biobank.*

Likewise, every collection must be assigned to a biobank, if not it raises a warning:

- *Orphaned collection*

Checks on the content of each collection:

- *Invalid ORPHA code found: %s" % (d['id'])). This warning raises when the provided ORPHAcode is not present in en_product1.xml from <http://www.orphadata.org/cgi-bin/ORPHAnomenclature.html>*
- *It seems that diagnoses contains range - this will render the diagnosis search ineffective for the given collection. Violating diagnosis term(s): xxx.*
- *Collection type not provided.*
- *Size of the collection does not match its order of magnitude: size = xxx, order of magnitude is xxx.*
- *Suspicious situation: large collection (> 100,000 samples or cases) without subcollections; unless it is a really homogeneous collection, it is advisable to refine such a collection into sub-collections to give users better insight into what is stored there.*
- *Suspicious situation: large collection (> 1,000,000 samples or cases) without exact size specified.*
- *No diagnoses provide for HOSPITAL or DISEASE_SPECIFIC or RD collection.*
- *Diagnoses provided but none of HOSPITAL, DISEASE_SPECIFIC, RD is specified as collection type (this may be easily false positive check).*
- *No material types are provided while biological samples are collected.*
- *Sample types advertised but BIOLOGICAL_SAMPLES missing among its data categories.*
- *No diagnoses provide for a collection with MEDICAL_RECORDS among its data categories.*
- *Diagnoses provided but no MEDICAL_RECORDS among its data categories.*
- *Rare disease (RD) collection without ORPHA code diagnoses.*
- *Consider adding following ORPHA code(s) to the RD collection - based on mapping ICD-10 code xxx to ORPHA codes: xxx.*
- *ORPHA code diagnoses provided, but collection not marked as rare disease (RD) collection.*
- *ORPHA code diagnoses specified, but no ICD-10 equivalents provided, thus making collection impossible to find for users using ICD-10 codes.*
- *ORPHA code xxx provided, but its translation to ICD-10 as xxx is not provided (mapping is of xxx type). It is recommended to provide this translation explicitly until Directory implements full semantic mapping search.*
- *No image modalities provided for image collection.*
- *No image dataset types provided for image collection.*
- *Imaging modalities or image data set found, but IMAGING_DATA is not among data categories: xxx.*
- *Ambiguous speification of age_unit - only one value is permitted. Provided values xxx.*
- *Missing age_unit for provided age range: xxx*
- *Age_high is below the minimum value limit (xxx): offending value xxx*
- *Age_low is below the minimum value limit (xxx): offending value xxx*
- *Age_low (xxx) is higher than age_high (xxx)*
- *Suspect situation: age_low == age_high == (xxx) (may be false positive)*

Contact information is checked as follows:

- *Missing first name for contact ('first_name' attribute is empty)*
- *Missing last name for contact ('last_name' attribute is empty)*
- *Missing email for contact ('email' attribute is empty)*
- *Email for contact is invalid - offending 'email' attribute value: xxx.*
- *Email for contact seems to be unreachable because of missing DNS MX record.*
- *Missing phone for contact ('phone' attribute is empty)*
- *Phone number for contact does not conform to the E.123 international standard (means starts with + sign, no spaces) - offending phone number in 'phone' attribute: xxx*

Existence of a biobank/collection name and description is needed. If not present:

- *Missing description for biobank ('description' attribute is empty for the biobank).*
- *Suspiciously short description for biobank ('description' attribute xxx has less than 3 words).*
- *Missing name for biobank ('name' attribute is empty for the biobank)*
- *Missing description for collection ('description' attribute is empty for the collection)*
- *Suspiciously short description for collection ('description' attribute xxx has less than 3 words).*
- *Missing name for collection ('name' attribute is empty for the biobank).*

IDs not compliant with the specifications at different levels are also caught:

- *BiobankID is not compliant with the specification (shall start with "bbmri-eric:ID:EXT_" prefix for external biobanks that have no national node).*
- *BiobankID is not compliant with the specification (shall start with "bbmri-eric:ID:EXT_" prefix for external biobanks).*
- *BiobankID is not compliant with the specification (shall start with "bbmri-eric:ID:NN_" prefix).*
- *BiobankID contains illegal characters (shall be "A-Za-z0-9:_-").*
- *BiobankID contains :: indicating empty component in ID hierarchy.*
- *CollectionID is not compliant with the specification (shall start with "bbmri-eric:ID:EXT_" prefix for collections from external biobanks that have no national node).*
- *CollectionID is not compliant with the specification (shall start with "bbmri-eric:ID:EXT_" prefix for collections from external biobanks).*
- *CollectionID is not compliant with the specification (shall start with "bbmri-eric:ID: NN_" prefix).*
- *CollectionID contains illegal characters (shall be "A-Za-z0-9:_-").*
- *CollectionID does not contain expected biobank prefix (should start with biobankID:collection:)*
- *CollectionID contains :: indicating empty component in ID hierarchy.*
- *ContactID is not compliant with the specification (shall start with "bbmri-eric:ID:EXT_" prefix for contacts for external biobanks that have no national node).*
- *ContactID is not compliant with the specification (shall start with "bbmri-eric:contactID:EXT_" prefix for contacts for external biobanks).*
- *ContactID is not compliant with the specification (shall start with "bbmri-eric:contactID:NN_" prefix).*
- *ContactID contains illegal characters (shall be "A-Za-z0-9:_-").*
- *ContactID contains :: indicating empty component in ID hierarchy.*
- *NetworkID is not compliant with the specification (shall start with "bbmri-eric:ID:EXT_" prefix for networks from countries that have no national node).*
- *NetworkID is not compliant with the specification (shall start with "bbmri-eric:networkID: prefix).*
- *NetworkID has suspicious country affiliation " + ' (should start with "bbmri-eric:networkID:NN_" or "bbmri-eric:networkID:EU_" prefix).*
- *NetworkID contains illegal characters (shall be "A-Za-z0-9:_-").*
- *NetworkID contains :: indicating empty component in ID hierarchy.*

Specific checks are done for COVID19-related biobanks or collections:

- *It seems that diagnosis contains range - this will render the diagnosis search ineffective for the given collection. Violating diagnosis term(s): xxx*

- *Biobank contains COVID collection xxx but not marked as part of the COVID19 network (bbmri-eric:networkID:EU_BBMRI-ERIC:networks:COVID19).*
- *Biobank contains COVID collection xxx but does not have "covid19" attribute in "covid19biobank" section of attributes.*
- *Collection type not provided.*
- *Prospective COVID-19 collections must have DISEASE_SPECIFIC as one of its types.*
- *Prospective COVID-19 collections must have PROSPECTIVE_COLLECTION as one of its types.*
- *Prospective collection type represents capability of setting up prospective collections - hence it should have zero order of magnitude.*
- *COVID19PROSPECTIVE collection misses COVID-19 diagnosis or COVID-19 controls filled in.*
- *Collection having "ability to collect" does not have COVID19PROSPECTIVE label.*
- *Prospective collection type represents capability of setting up prospective collections - hence it should have zero order of magnitude.*
- *Existing COVID-19 collections must have DISEASE_SPECIFIC as one of its types.*
- *Suspect material types: existing COVID-19 collection does not have any of the common material types: DNA, PATHOGEN, PERIPHERAL_BLOOD_CELLS, PLASMA, RNA, SALIVA, SERUM, WHOLE_BLOOD, FECES, BUFFY_COAT, NASAL_SWAB, THROAT_SWAB.*
- *Suspect situation: collection contains infectious material (nasal/throat swabs, faeces) while the parent biobank does not indicate BSL2 nor BSL3 available.*
- *COVID19 collection misses COVID-19 diagnosis filled in.*
- *Biobank is part of COVID19 network (bbmri-eric:networkID:EU_BBMRI-ERIC:networks:COVID19) but does not have covid19 among covid19biobank attributes.*
- *Biobank has covid19 among covid19biobank attributes but is not part of COVID19 network (bbmri-eric:networkID:EU_BBMRI-ERIC:networks:COVID19).*
- *Biobank has covid19 among covid19biobank but has no relevant services nor any collection of COVID-19 samples nor any collection of COVID-19 controls.*
- *Biobank has ProspectiveCollections among covid19biobank attributes but has no prospective collection defined (collection ID matching '.*:COVID19PROSPECTIVE\$' regex pattern)")*
- *Biobank has prospective COVID-19 collection defined but ProspectiveCollections is not among covid19biobank attributes.*

If the biobank URL is not present, a warning will show up: *Missing URL*. In addition, provided URLs for biobanks and for data, sample and image access within collections are tested, raising these warnings in case of failure:

- *URL does not start with http or https.*
- *URL was not accessed successfully*
- *URL is misformatted*
- *URL produced connection aborted by peer*
- *URL produced connection refused by peer*
- *URL produced connection reset by peer*
- *URL returns non-success code (returns HTTP error code: xxx)*